

RERAM

research to innovation in
resource efficiency

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Wood Innovation Toolkit

Worksheets, Checklists, Lectures and Manuals
for Resource Efficiency Checks and Trainings of
SMEs in the ENP-EaP forest-based sector

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1. Purpose and objectives

The objective of Task 4.3 was to develop a kit of low-level tools that can support decision making in resource efficiency in the forest-based sector of ENP-EaP countries. This deliverable report D4.3 collects a set of tools and guidelines, which allow company owners, production managers and product developers in the woodworking sector to innovate their business and processes in terms of raw material use, resource and energy efficiency.

The toolkit is based on the Austrian ÖKOPROFIT method (Stadt Graz Umweltamt 2004). It has been adapted to the needs of ENP companies, based on the findings of the on-spot checks of 19 woodworking companies, conducted by the RERAM consultants under the supervision of the HCS Holzcluster Steiermark GmbH from 2014-2016 (see more details in the report D3.3 'Reality check and benchmarking').

The set of tools allows managers to target a “win-win” situation, to make their business more efficient and at the same time more environmental friendly. Basically it supports the manager in decisions on which improvement steps to take and in which correct order to take them, by respecting the given constraints on budgets, resources, human skills, and short term profitability of the company.

The tools can be applied by managers, consultants and intermediaries for their own purposes. However, the best recommended approach for successful cleaner production projects is to start a cooperation with external advisors (consultants, intermediaries).

The objectives of the RERAM toolkit are the following:

- ✓ Collect relevant production and process data as starting point for CP projects
- ✓ Regular monitoring of production and process parameters with direct impact on profit, environment, and worker safety
- ✓ Identify “hidden” costs and waste streams
- ✓ Reduce production costs for the same product output
- ✓ Improve process flow and reduce lead times
- ✓ Reduce regulatory non-compliance risks
- ✓ Improve environmental and workplace quality (less emissions, worker health)
- ✓ Increase employee morale and commitment
- ✓ Meet customer expectations in terms of product quality and environmental impact
- ✓ Support environmental communication to clients and administration

The toolkit comprises Worksheets, Checklists, Training Lectures and Manuals, which are available in English and partly in Russian language (which was chosen for practical reasons to attain a broader audience in the ENP-EaP countries). The main CP introduction and several selected chapters have also been translated into Romanian and Georgian language. All material is available online from: www.reram.eu.

2. Introduction

The importance of Cleaner Production and the situation in ENP-EaP countries

The Cleaner Production (CP) concept pursues a “win-win” approach by implementing cost-effective, preventive measures to waste control that makes efficient use of energy and materials by reducing risks to health and safety. The benefits of this concept have been documented for different companies and stakeholders across all industrial sectors (e.g. BTG 2014, ECOLOGIC 2012, UNEP 2011, European Commission 2011, Commerzbank 2011). The main Cleaner Production characteristics are:

- Entrepreneurs benefit from a reduction of input material and production costs, fewer expenses for waste handling and disposal, higher production efficiencies, lower maintenance and cleaning efforts, and reduced risks of payments and penalties for pollution.
- Employees benefit from a higher work place safety and health, and lower working strain.
- The general public benefits from minimized environmental pollution, eco-friendlier products, and improved living conditions (air, water, dumping grounds, etc.). This in turn will be mirrored by a “license to operate”.

The experience from CP projects shows that achieving these benefits requires a change in the mindset of enterprise managers to gain a real, sustained commitment - ideally reflected in a long term strategy; otherwise the implementation of the CP technology has only a temporary character with pilot projects stopping after phasing out.

Successful CP implementation can be defined as a **preventive AND continuous process** to improve process efficiency and increase overall yield of final products. Cleaner production processes must be oriented to reduction of environmental impact caused by production process at the source rather than at the “end of the pipe”. This can be reached by monitoring and reduction of the pollutant and waste generation at several stages of production process.

With respect to the **RERAM project**, the comparison of findings of company checks between Austria (benchmark reference country) and the three surveyed ENP-EaP countries (Georgia, Moldova, Ukraine) has led to **the following conclusions regarding the situation in the ENP-EaP countries:**

- Cleaner production approach was completely unknown in the ENP countries
- Very low environmental awareness in the wood working industry (and in general)
- Highly production (output) oriented with end-of-pipe thinking instead of preventive approaches
- Joint venture companies showed a higher level of production organization, better material handling and work place quality (observed only in Ukraine).

- Company managers are usually not educated in wood working, whereas company owners often showed a short-term profit oriented attitude (very few of the companies visited were more than 10 years on the market)
- Low managerial skills on work shop and production process organization
- Low skills and competences of the work force in wood working
- Lack of maintenance efforts and/or knowledge on maintenance
- Second hand equipment (but usually from well-known European and Asian manufacturers)
- Poor work place and air quality conditions (health, safety, significant risks of fire/explosion with two severe fire incidents in companies checked between 03/2015-05/2016)
- Low level of national regulations on waste (no requirements for waste separation systems, companies reported that costs for waste disposal are based on lump sums and not by volume) and work place safety
- Timber supply problems have often led to the substitution of domestic solid wood with imported wood panels (chipboard, MDF), import of veneers and semi-finished solid wood products (absence of modern sawmills with drying chambers)
- Auxiliary materials are often imported (paint, glue, textiles)
- Unsatisfying thermal and heating situation due to the use of outdated (yet cheap and abundant) work shop facilities from the communistic era
- No resource, waste or cost monitoring systems in place
- No energy monitoring in place

The company finding reports were presented and explained to company representatives, whereas the aggregated findings were discussed in panel sessions with a larger audience from business and administration. In addition, feedback, recommendations and training sessions on the most pressing topics related to raw material and resource efficiency were held (see the reports D3.3 'Reality Checks and Benchmarking' and D4.2 'R2I Dialogues').

Considering the difficult situation in ENP countries, the recommendations of the RERAM experts focused on **good housekeeping measures** (no-to-low cash investment with payoff period of less than 1 year) as the first steps towards the implementation of CP options. While most entrepreneurs easily understood the benefits of the CP approach for their company, there were concerns and uncertainties on where to start given the magnitude of potentials and options for improvements.

Therefore, the RERAM consortium put together a **low-level wood industry toolkit** for entrepreneurs, local consultants and intermediaries to collect, analyze and monitor their raw material and resource consumption patterns along with information on the waste streams generated. Based on the analysis, the tools allow to identify the "low-hanging fruits" (large potentials with no investments) and to decide on targets for first CP projects.

The following chapters contain the collection of tools in the form of worksheets, checklists, training lectures and manuals. The final chapter contains a collection of further useful tools and literature.

3. Worksheets

The toolkit comprises detailed worksheets for:

- Main raw and processed materials consumed
- Solid waste and other emissions
- Main products and/or services
- Main energy consumers (machine list)
- Energy consumption pattern
- Pressurized Air Leakage Test and Calculation Tool
- Checklist for Resource Efficiency (self-assessment)
- Special chapter on Eco-design

3.1 Monitoring main raw and processed materials

A profound overview and analysis of input materials (e.g. solid wood, wood panels, semi-finished wood products) or any other kind of input (e.g. water, non-wood materials) is essential as the first step to any further decision making on how to improve resource efficiency of your company.

In order to reduce the complexity of tracking your material inputs, clear boundaries have to set accordingly. System boundaries can be set on machine level, process level, production unit or on a whole workshop.

Based on the worksheet “Main raw and processed materials” (Tool W.1), the input materials with high volumes, value or toxicity can be identified and selected for a deeper material flow analysis. Material flow analysis provides very detailed insight into any kind of process and should always be carried out in cooperation with an external adviser (e.g. a consultant, a university, or an intermediary), because the measuring, accounting and visualization requires substantial professional experience. Besides material balances, also energy balances can be carried out as well by means of input-output analysis.

The tool “Worksheet Raw Materials” together with a material flow analysis can provide answers to the questions *how much of my raw material is used respectively wasted in a production step*. It allows for a targeted measurement as a basis to improve efficiencies and/or environmental friendliness of the process.

Tool W.1 Worksheet on raw and processed materials

Worksheet for monitoring main raw and processed materials									
Company:									
Person in charge:									
Last update:									
Period considered:									
No.	Raw material (max. 10)	Quantity purchased	Quantity used	In stock	Unit	Costs/Unit	Total costs	Purpose/use	% incorporated into the product
1									
2									
3									
4									
5									
6									
7									
8									

For the initial step it is recommended to focus on the 10 most important input materials. Importance can be defined either by volume, price or harmfulness of the material. For primary wood working industries (sawmills, solid wood panel producers) usually solid wood is the most important input by costs (70% - 50% share of the total production costs) and by volume.

<i>Field to fill in</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
Raw material	Description of the input material
Quantity purchased	Total amount purchased in a given time period
Quantity used / in stock	Quantities used in the production step, inventory list required for in stock quantities
Purpose/use	Description of output of the production process
% incorporated into the product	Estimate of the amount of input material remaining as a "product" after processing

3.2 Monitoring all types of waste and emissions

This is one of the most important tools and constitutes a must to be filled in because only the amount of waste tells the “real” story of production processes and their efficiencies. Waste incurs significant costs in production processes due to several reasons:

- Every waste was once an input material that had to be purchased
- Handling of waste is one of the big “hidden” costs and always has a negative impact on productivity
- Direct costs of waste disposal
- Might be a problem for health and worker safety

Often the purchase of higher quality input material pays off through higher productivity, material efficiency, and a lower amount of rejected goods. Furthermore, companies should always try to substitute hazardous materials with less hazardous materials fulfilling the same purpose.

When analyzing the waste fractions always ask where the waste comes from: Which production step is concerned? Which product is concerned? Following the cleaner production approach try to deal with waste in the following order:

1. Reduce
2. Reuse
3. Recycle
4. Dispose

For the steps 2-4 it is important to implement a waste separation system in your company. Waste fractions without any internal use may still be sold (or given away for free) to a client, which may save disposal costs and handling efforts.

Tool W.2 Worksheet on waste

Worksheet for monitoring all types of waste and emissions						
Company:						
Person in charge:						
Last update:						
Period considered: <small>(usually 1 year)</small>						
No.	Waste (solid, liquid or gaseous state)	Quantity	Unit	Purchasing costs	Disposal costs	Total cost
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						
7						
8						

<i>Field to fill in</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
Waste	Description of the waste stream
Quantity and Unit	Amount of waste
Purchasing costs	Equivalent cost of the former input material
Disposal costs	Real costs for disposal. Virtual costs for disposal may also be used for scenario techniques
Total costs	Sum of all costs

3.3 Main products and/or services

This worksheet helps to identify and to rank the most important products by unit (pieces, volume, weight, etc.). It is recommended to start with 5-8 products only and to break down those products into their main components.

The result of this tool will be reflected by the work sheet on “Waste streams” and may provide an insight into efficiency rates with respect to the total product or to single components.

Tool W.3 Worksheet on products

Worksheet main products/services			
Company:			
Person in charge:			
Last update:			
Period considered:			
No.	Product or service	Annual quantity	Unit
1			
2			
3			
4			

<i>Field to fill in</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
Product (or service)	Description of the product
Amount quantity	Number of pieces or overall volume. Additionally, it is recommended to break down the product into single parts (incl. surface treatment, glue, etc.). If known and reasonable, a quantification of the single parts shall be provided
Unit	Should be as accurate as possible e.g. volume or weight should be preferred over pieces

3.4 Monitoring Energy consumers (machine list)

In comparison to many other industrial sectors the wood working industries show rather low energy consumption per volume of raw material processed. The main energy is consumed by drying processes and transport activities (both internal and external transports). Nevertheless, energy consumption and energy costs constitute an important cost item in forest-based industries. Apart from economic reasons, there are sound ecological arguments calling for a reduction of energy stemming from fossil fuels, coal or nuclear power plants. Unfortunately, the energy topic is still dealt poorly in most small to medium sized companies in forest industries leaving energy and cost saving potentials untapped.

The current situation shows, that electric metering in wood working companies is done on a very general level, either at firm gate or in rare cases per production unit. In case of modern machinery internal counters indicate operating hours, but this information is hardly used for further analysis.

For an effective energy management, companies require regular information not only on the main consumers and the total energy consumption in kWh, but also on the time response and amount of the so-called peak load in kW. The peak load must be fixed with the energy provider and is paid by the number of total kW. In case the agreed peak load is overrun, the companies have to pay penalties on the overrun for the given contract time.

As it is not economically feasible to meter every single machine, a machine list with the main consumers, their performance plate data, start and stop times can greatly help to understand and optimize a company's energy consumption. A comparison between the machine list and the energy invoice will help companies to detect:

- Main consumers of energy by kWh and uptime
- Hidden energy consumers in case of significant deviations between the machine list data and the energy invoice
- Discrepancies between actual energy consumption and the energy invoice

A machine list also helps to take the right decisions when it comes to the replacement/upgrade of the machinery in terms of energy efficiency/consumption. Furthermore, the analysis of the power ratings (kW) per machines and their start-stop times can help to avoid load peak overruns resp. reduces the overall peak load required (which has to be paid for). For instance, a typical measure to smooth out peak loads/avoid overruns is to set slightly different work break times for the working staff of different production units.

Please note that the worksheet uses kWh as unit for the energy consumption. In case you have other fuel-powered machinery you can find a conversion tool into kWh here: [www.seai.ie/Your Business/Public Sector/Reporting/AnnualReport/Energy_Consumption_Calculation_Tool.xls](http://www.seai.ie/Your_Business/Public_Sector/Reporting/AnnualReport/Energy_Consumption_Calculation_Tool.xls)

Tool W.4 Worksheet on Energy Consumers

Worksheet Energy consumers											
Company:											
Person in charge:											
Last update:											
Period considered: <small>(usually 1 year)</small>											
No .	Description of machinery	Year of constr.	Power in kW	Cos phi	Start time	Stop time	hours per year	Variable Speed	Energy consumption [kWh/y]	% of total consumption	Notes
1											
2											
3											
4											
5											

For filling in the worksheet only focus on the major consumers – there is no need to specify small equipment (e.g. hand tools or stationary machinery with low power rating). As a rule of thumb less than 10 machines will result in up to 90% of the energy consumption. In case you have several workshops, one document per production facility is recommended.

<i>Field to fill in</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
Description of machine	Short description of the machine (purpose, manufacturer)
Year of construction	see machine performance plate
Powers in kW	see machine performance plate
Cos phi	reactive power rating, see machine performance plate
Start and Stop time	Estimated turn on/off time/s of the machine (important to detect peak times of consumption)
Variable speed	yes/no (does the motor run at a fixed or variable speed depending on load)
Energy consumption (annual uptime)	kWh/year (by electric submitters, by uptime counter or by own estimation)
% of total consumption	automatically calculated, percentage of the total energy consumption
Notes	any useful piece of information (last maintenance/fixture work, replacement of spare part, etc.)

3.5 Monitoring Energy consumption patterns

This worksheet is closely related to the Table 4 “Energy consumers (machine list)”, but breaks down a company’s energy consumption by types of fuel rather than by machine type.

A significant deviation between the energy consumption patterns and the total energy consumption listed in “Energy consumers (machine list)” may indicate that essential consumers are missing (or hidden), resp. require further reasoning and investigation.

The overview on consumption patterns allow for decisions on energy saving measures as well as on the substitution of fuels. For instance, a substitution of gasoline/diesel driven transport vehicles with electric-powered transport vehicles usually pays off in a few years. Table 1 shows a comparison of energy consumption, operations costs and CO₂ emissions between diesel and electrical fork lifts of comparable maximum lift weight. The calculation was done for Austrian companies in 2010.

Table 1. Energy consumption, operation costs and CO₂ emissions of forklifts

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Diesel forklift</i>	<i>Electrical forklift</i>
Energy consumption per h	28 kWh	7 kWh
Operation costs per h	23 €	0,7 €
CO ₂ emissions per h	7,9 kg	4,2 kg

Source: WIN 2010

It is notable that the efficiency of electrical drives is much higher than that of diesel drives which is also reflected in less CO₂ emissions. However, the significant difference in operations costs per hour stems from less maintenance and repair work for electrical fork lifts and only to a smaller part from differences in fuel prices.

Limitations for electric vehicles are mainly the presence of slopes or very uneven terrain at the company premises.

Tool W.5 *Worksheet on energy consumption patterns*

Worksheet for monitoring energy consumption patterns											
Company:											
Person in charge:											
Last update:											
Period considered: <small>(usually 1 year)</small>											
No.	Energy		Amount	Unit	Costs/Unit	Conversion into kWh	Consumption in kWh	Share in%	Total costs	Share in%	
1	Electricity	Consumption		kWh							
		Peak load		kW							
2	District heating	Consumption		kWh							
		Peak load		kW							
3	Oil			l		x 11.4					
4	Gas			m ³		x 10.0					
5				kWh							
6										
7										
8	Fuels	Diesel		Litre		x 10.0					
		Petrol		Litre		x 9.0					
9										
10										
Total:									100%		100%

The worksheet offers a simple possibility to convert energy units into [kWh]. For most types of energy the provided conversion rates should be fine. In case a more sophisticated conversion tool is required, the Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland offers a free tool: www.seai.ie/Your_Business/Public_Sector/Reporting/AnnualReport/Energy_Consumption_Calculation_Tool.xls

3.6 Monitoring compressed air system leak volume and costs

Tool W.6 Compressor test

A) Measurement step

Pre-requisites:

Figure 1 Pre-requisites for the compressed air leakage test

Step 1: Make sure that no compressed air is used and the compressor is turned on. This way all the compressed air demand comes from the leaks only. Wait until the last loading process is finished (listen when the compressor stops working). The air receiver is now fully loaded.

Step 2: Use a stopwatch to take time how long the compressor is unloading or stopped and how long it is loading. With smaller compressors usually 5 minutes are enough, while the time measurement for big compressors - or in case of large storage capacities - may take longer.

Figure 2 Time measurement for the compressed air leakage test

Step 3: Repeat the measurement to make sure you get a minimum of 2-3 cycles – one cycle corresponds to a full unload-stop-load pattern. Since the leaks do not really change, the load-unload-stop cycle should be quite steady. Record the data in the list below.

Cycles	unloading Time	t_{load} = loading Time	
1			
2			
3			
...n			T_{period} = measuring periode
n= numbers of cycles	Σ	+ Σ	= Σ

Figure 3 Calculation of loading and unloading times

Step 4: Repeat the measurement for every compressor in your company.

B) Analysis

Calculate the leakage in % according to the following formula:

$$Leak \% = n * \frac{t_{load}}{T_{period}} * 100$$

With:

n ... number of full cycles within the measuring period

t_{load} ... load time of the compressor in *seconds*

T_{period} ... measuring period in *seconds*

Example: Within 10 minutes (T) measuring period the compressor runs 4 times on full load for about 30 seconds of each load time. Therefore, the leakage is

$$Leak \% = 4 * 30 / 600 * 100 = 20\%$$

As a rule of thumb a compressed air system is considered as reasonable tight if the leakage is below 10%.

Calculate the losses per year in costs based on estimated working hours (common case)

$$Money\ losses = Leak \% * Hours_{comp} * maxP_{comp} * costs\ per\ kWh$$

With:

Money losses ... *local currency/year*

$Hours_{comp}$... Estimated annual working hours of the compressor in *h/year* [usually based on assumptions]

$maxP_{comp}$... Power rating of the compressor in *kW* (see performance plate)

Example Austria:

With 20% leakages, a power rating of 11 kW and working hours of 4000 h/year the losses are as follows (price for 1 kWh was estimated to 0,12 €):

$$\text{Money losses} = 0,2 * 4000 * 11 * 0,12 = 1.056 \text{ €/year}$$

Calculation based on meter data of the energy consumption of the compressor

Although most commonly meter data is not available, an electric meter can be rented for a day or a week to have accurate consumption data for the calculation of money losses.

$$\text{Money losses} = \text{Leak \%} * \text{Energy}_{365} * \text{costs per kWh}$$

With:

Money losses ... local currency/year

Energy₃₆₅ ... annual energy consumption of the compressor in kWh [metered]

Example Austria:

With 20% leakages and an annual energy consumption of 44000 kWh/year the losses are as follows (price for 1 kWh was estimated to 0,12 €):

$$\text{Money losses} = 0,2 * 44000 * 0,12 = 1.056 \text{ €/year}$$

4. Checklists for Self-Assessment

The following checklists are a good starting point for a company to check all aspects of raw material and resource efficiency and to discuss further steps with external advisors. It comprises the topics: Organisation, Product issues, Procurement, Resource efficiency, Hazardous substances, Energy, Water, and Waste Management.

Tool C.1 Checklist Organisation

C.1		Checklist (Organisation)		Page 1 of 44
Contact person in the company:				
n.	Organisation	Remarks	Realisation	
1.	Do you know about your legal requirements (e.g. limits) and how do you fulfil them?	Do you have list? Do you monitor and report monthly the status of compliance? National, Local, international, industry regulations		
2.	Are the environmental indicators regarding the use of materials and the emissions used as instrument of controlling?	KWH/ person M ³ / person KG of waste /person used in financial / envir. accounting		
3.	Is there an environmental benchmarking process in charge with respect to the product?	KWH/unit/kg M ³ /unit/kg Kg waste/unit/client		
4.	Are the environmental costs and the environmental revenues listed in the accounting department?	Cost – disposal cost of haz mat/ garbage collection cost/ cost of waste treatment/ penalty of spills		
5.	Is there one responsible person for environmental issues and representative with sufficient competence and power to give instructions?			
6.	Has an environmental team been founded?			
7.	Is the management involved and /or informed about environmental issues?			
8.	Is the awareness regarding Resource Efficiency actively supported to increase the motivation within the company? (e.g. idea competition)	Is there suggestions scheme/ Lean programs		
9.	Will further training in environmental related issues be used?	Is it part of career devt / regulations / training plan		
10.	Additional remarks:			

Tool C.2 Checklist Product issues

C.2	Checklist Product issues		Page 2 of 44
Contact person in the company:			
n.	Product issues	Remarks:	Realisation
1.	Are there any methods to show if there are any pollutants in products?	Do you have list of haz waste	
2.	Are there methods for disposal, recycling, utilisation after use?	Do you have waste water treatment, do you have solid waste compactor, do you reuse or recycle	
3.	Are there methods to avoid unwanted by-products?	Do you consider alternative items to lessen by products? Or do you source out to recycling agency to use them?	
4.	Will recycled material be used for products and packaging?		
5.	Are energy balances for individual products available?	KWH/unit/kg M ³ /unit/kg	
6.	Are returnable containers used for transportation?		
7.	Which environmental issues are considered during planning of production facilities?	Do you consider wind thermodynamics, ventilation system, illumination or natural lighting system	
8.	Which environmental issues are considered during product development process?	Use of sustainable material as part of the product; or other indirect materials which are environment friendly (eg. styro to starch, etc.)	
	Additional remarks:		

Tool C.3 Checklist Procurement

C.3	Checklist Procurement		Page 3 of 44
Contact person in the company:			
n.	Procurement	Remarks	<i>Realisation</i>
1.	Do environmental purchasing guidelines for materials exist? If so what issues are addressed?	Do you have green purchasing guidelines? Is this established by mother company or internally? MSDS, control of Hazmat, alternative mat'ls, Life Cycle analysis	
2.	By purchasing do you pay attention to the marking of the products?	CE label, UL label, Eco friendly label, ways of recycling	
3.	Do you ask for safety data sheets?	Have you identified what materials really needs MSDS	
4.	Are there any guidelines to keep safety data sheets up to date and forward those accurately?	MSDS should be updated coz some of the materials may not be haz last year which is now included in the list of haz mat	
5.	Do you have agreements with your suppliers regarding the packaging?	Drums or palette can be returned to suppliers and if you can ask for a markdown on price since they will save cost on packaging	
6.	Do you check new materials before the first use in the company on environmental issues?	Is there qualification procedure for new products?	
7.	Additional remarks:		

Tool C.4 Checklist Resource Efficiency

C.4		Checklist Resource efficiency		Page 4 of 44
Contact person in the company:				
n.	Resource efficiency	Remarks	Realisation	
1.	Is the careful use of matters/materials intended?	Programs such as energy / raw materials conservation		
2.	Are there any matter balances on company, product and process basis to establish disposition?	Do you conduct MFA analysis		
3.	Is there a periodic actualisation of a central list of all inputs ?	All inputs are recorded in your financial statement (total energy, electric, water, materials etc.)		
4.	Is there a periodic actualisation of a central list of all outputs ?	Do you conduct MFA analysis to determine how much energy / material is included in the output product e.g. paint		
5.	Are there certain personal responsibilities for the field of matters and materials?	Do you practice material inventory system,		
6.	Do you have a materials efficiency product benchmarking in charge?	What is the main material? Do you have monitoring of it per product?		
7.	How much energy is incorporated in your product? What kinds of energy?	Electric / fuel / gas needed to produce your product or to deliver your service		
8.	How much water is used per product unit?	M ³ per unit/piece/kg Monitoring must include domestic use, gardening, etc.		
9.	Are there certain methods to store and transport products environmentally friendly?	Do you consider carton mould instead of styro packaging or the use of eco-plastic		
10.	Do you optimise your raw material delivery to minimise inventory and storage time?	To avoid degradation..		
11.	Do you inspect and sort your raw material (wood)?	Sort by length, thickness, and quality to reduce wood waste		
12.	Do you separate wood by sticks when stacking? Do you use "stick guides" to align the sticks?	This allows it to dry and prevents staining and rotting that results in wasted wood. If the kiln sticks are not perfectly aligned, deformation of the wood can occur and creating waste		

C.4		Checklist Resource efficiency		Page 5 of 44
Contact person in the company:				
13.	Do you practice "finger jointing"?	joining of two short sticks or boards end-to-end		
14.	Which recycling options of wood waste and sawdust do you use?	Particle board, laminates, animal bedding, mulch/ landscaping material, absorptive material, fuel (pellets, chips...),....		
15.	Do you have a maintenance plan for your machines/tools?	Avoidance of waste due to wear of tools etc..		
16.	Which application technology do you use? Are your workers well trained?	High pressure, HVLP, Airless, electrostatic, etc... Application efficiency known?		
17.	Are there some certain corrective actions if there are some abnormalities?	Abnormalities such as over consumption of electricity/fuel/gas/ high material consumption?		
18.	Already implemented efficiency measures and additional remarks:			

Tool C.5 Checklist Hazardous Substances

C.5		Checklist Hazardous substances		Page 6 of 44
Contact person in the company:				
n.	Hazardous sub-stances	Remarks	Realisation	
1.	Who is responsible for dealing with the matter of hazardous substances?	Is there an appointed person?		
2.	Are all hazardous substances recorded in a special record?	Haz mats includes paints, fluorescent, styro and cleaning materials		
3.	Are there available safety data sheets for all hazardous substances?	Do you have person to review the MSDS before purchasing the materials		
4.	Are materials containing hazardous substances transported in an appropriate way?	Do you specify the storage condition or packaging materials before transport		
5.	Are materials containing hazardous components stored in an appropriate way (especially toxic materials and fire hazard materials)?	Is there a secondary catchment, firewall... depends on what type of chemicals if fire hazards, health hazards or environment hazards Lid always closed?		
6.	Do you have instructions in a written way of how to handle hazardous substances?	Do you have work instruction?		
7.	Do you inform and train your staff regularly how to handle dangerous materials?	How do you conduct the training?		
8.	Do you do an evaluation of risks of hazardous substances in regular intervals? (Place of work specific risk judgement)?			
9.	Which measures you have implemented to reduce the amount of hazardous substances or to make the work with these materials safer?	Have you checked for alternative materials?		
10.	Where do the materials containing hazardous substances end up? - product? - waste? - wastewater? - gaseous emissions?			
11.	Additional remarks:			

Tool C.6 Checklist Energy

C.6	Checklist Energy		Page 7 of 44
Contact person in the company:			
n.	Energy	Remarks	Realisation
1.	Is there a central record about the energy consumption per year from the different energy sources?	Is it included in the Financial Statement... Who is energy supplier? Solar, genset, wind, etc.	
2.	Is somebody responsible in the area of energy?		
3.	Which energy saving measures are already in place? (warm water, process heat, room heat)?	Programs like turning off of lights/ACU/ info campaign about correct temp settings	
4.	Are there energy indicators and are they used as in company controlling instrument?	KWH/unit/kg Or KWH / person	
5.	Are there records about weekly or daily load measurements? Are these used for analysis?	Do you have separate monitoring aside from the monthly billing? Report & analysis	
6.	How is energy consumption monitored?	Per cost center? Per department? Monthly? Daily?	
7.	What are the cost relevant details of your energy supply contract (peak load charged?)? What are they like?	Ask for peak load graph from supplier... Analyze and conduct cascade switching	
8.	Is there a record about the energy data of the single consumer (e.g. machine list)?	Do you have an Equipment Inventory List (Name/Wattage/Ratings/Utility Factor/operating hour)	
9.	Is there a record with the comparison of target value and actual value?	Do you conduct monthly reporting/review	
10.	Is the actualisation of the energy record secured?		
11.	Is there a load management for electricity? Is it regularly maintained?		
12.	Is the lighting system optimised? (natural lighting, T5 bulbs, electronic ballasts, LED, sensors, height of lights,...)		

C.6		Checklist (Energy)		Page 8 of 44
Contact person in the company:				
n.	Energy	Remarks	<i>Realisation</i>	
13.	Do you use VFD/VSD or frequency converters (at compressor, pumps, fans, big motors)?			
14.	Can you regulate your dust extraction system? (close unused pipes, etc.)			
15.	Do you switch off machines during idle times and breaks?			
16.	Do you have a waste heat recovery? (Heat exchangers)	Where do you use the waste heat?		
17.	Are your cooling machines analysed regarding the consumption of energy and cooling agent?	Do you have chillers? What capacity? Do you use CFC based Freon		
18.	Will the compressed-air grid be maintained regularly?	Air vessel closed after work? Do all members have access in reporting abnormalities?		
19.	Is the produced pressure in the compressed-air system as low as possible?	Do you have pressure regulating valves? What's the pressure drop?		
20.	Will the steam grid be maintained regularly? (Check for leaks, damaged insulation)	Do you use steam engine? For what use? How do you maintain it?		
21.	Do you have a condensate recovery system and/or an economizer in your steam system?	What's the flue gas temperature?		
22.	Are there some correction schemes for all possible abnormalities?	Air leaks?		
23.	Is there an intention to increase the use of renewable energies?	Wind, solar, solatube, etc.		
24.	Do you think there are some optimisation potentials?			
25.	Already implemented energy efficiency measures and additional remarks:			

Tool C.7 Checklist Water

C.7	Checklist (Water / Wastewater)		Page 9 of 44
Contact person in the company:			
n.	Water management	Remarks	<i>Realisation</i>
1.	Is the careful use of water guaranteed?	What programs do you implement?	
2.	Are there some water balances about the destination of water (company, product and process level)?	Water usage on a per dept/process/area Accounting of water per person	
3.	Is the careful use of water in adjacent areas guaranteed too?	Adjacent means garden, grounds, pavements, canteen, washing of hands	
4.	Are there records about water consumption and will it be updated regularly?	Monthly monitoring and reporting	
5.	Is there a documentation related to a comparison of target value and actual value?	Monthly monitoring and reporting	
6.	How are responsibilities shared concerning water consumption and wastewater?	Do you post signage or give pamphlets to all members	
7.	What kind of waste water treatment facilities do you have?	Do you use anaerobic or aerobic type? What type of chemical are you using? What checking method is done to verify effluent status	
8.	Will be determined which facilities are relevant in water and which directives have to be met?	E.g. Taps, toilets, shower rooms Do you have rules how to utilize water	
9.	How will be determined that current limits are met, state-of-the-art is used and own objectives will be met?	E.g. New toilet tanks, waterless urinals, mechanical footswitch, sensors	
10.	Are correction methods defined for all possible abnormalities (limits, state-of-the-art,...)?	Do you regularly check if there's water leaks in the pipeline, faulty drain, faulty valves	
11.	Do you think there are some optimisation potentials?	Use of microfiber rags, rainwater harvesting	
12.	Already implemented efficiency measures and additional remarks:		

Tool C.8 Checklist Waste Management

C.8		Checklist (Waste management)		Page 10 of 10
Contact person in the company:				
n.	Waste management	Remarks	<i>Realisation</i>	
1.	Do you know the regulations concerning waste management?			
2.	What are your main waste streams?	Type of waste? Do you pay or sell waste?		
3.	Is somebody responsible for the field of waste management?			
4.	How do you determine which facilities are relevant for waste? Which directives have to be fulfilled?	State of the art such as can crusher, styro compactor		
5.	How will be determined which laws and state-of-the-art and own guidelines will be met?			
6.	Is biodegradable waste collected separately?			
7.	Are correction methods available for all possible abnormalities (limits, state-of-the-art,...)?	If there are spills, or penalty occurrence		
8.	Do the waste streams contain any hazardous compounds? Which? How much? Where does the waste end up?	Do you conduct chemical lab for haz waste? Do you account haz waste disposal?		
9.	Do you think there are some optimisation potentials?			
10.	Already implemented efficiency measures and additional remarks:			

5. Special chapter Eco-design

5.1 Understanding the idea of Eco-design

The basic idea of Eco-design is to improve the product design in order to reduce the environmental impact throughout entire product life cycles (cradle-to-cradle product innovation). Improving products with Eco-design requires life cycle thinking, a target-oriented search for effective improvement strategies, a selection of successful measures and an efficient implementation of these measures in the ongoing planning, decision-making and management processes of a company.

Life cycle thinking is the essential basis of Eco-design. Only if the complete life cycle of a product from production to disposal is taken into account, an assessment of the environmental performance (and the costs involved) can be made:

- Extraction of raw materials
- Production of materials
- Manufacturing of parts
- Manufacturing of semi-finished products and components
- Assembly of the end product
- Distribution
- Use and maintenance
- End-of-life treatment (reuse, disassembly, material and chemical recycling, energy recovery, ultimate disposal)

This approach helps to identify trade-offs in the life cycle, and, therefore, to avoid the displacement of impacts from one life cycle stage to another which may lead to an overall negative change in the product. On the other hand, life cycle thinking aids to identification of the relevant “hot spots” in the life cycle of a product, therefore enabling the designer to focus on the most relevant issues. Consequently, the resources used in design can be used efficiently in order to improve the environmental performance of a product.

In addition, if the complete life cycle is considered, potentials for economic savings can also be determined, going far beyond traditional accounting procedures because the costs of the customer during use and end-of-life are also taken into account.

5.2 Legal Compliance – the baseline for Eco-design

Legal compliance is a “must” and a major driver for environmental efforts. Several directives and laws apply worldwide in the field of environmental protection. The most important product-related policies and legislation are:

- IPP Integrated Product Policy
- EuP – Eco-Design for Energy-using Products Directive
- WEEE – Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Directive
- RoHS – Restriction of the use of certain Hazardous Substances Directive

In recent years the European Union has pushed forward several of these activities for environmental legislation. Whereas the IPP is an overall policy outlining the framework and philosophy of product-related environmental legislation on European level, the directives set out the detailed requirements which are relevant for companies.

5.3 Environmental Management Systems and Eco-design

According to the European EMAS (Environmental Management and Audit Scheme) or ISO 14001, environmental management systems (EMS) traditionally set the focus on cleaner production measures; however, there are also overlaps with Eco-design. Hence, an EMS is an appropriate starting point to engage more in product related Eco-design.

To make the environmental performance of an enterprise comparable over time, key figures are frequently based on some kind of “production unit”. Such key figures might be energy or water consumption, specific chemicals consumption or (hazardous) waste generation with reference to, for example:

- “m² PCB area” (an appropriate key figure for a PCB – printed circuit board manufacturer)
- “m² silicon area” or “m² silicon area per mask layer” (semiconductor fab or ASIC design house – although a design house does not process wafers itself)
- “component” (passive components manufacturer)
- “product” (although this key figure might yet be too unspecific)

With such key figures, a product related benchmark can be established. To improve these key figures, targets can be set within an environmental management system and this is also a first step towards product improvements and eco-design, although it should be noted that such production related figures lack the life cycle perspective.

5.4 Eco-design Principles

Principles for Eco-design according to Charter & Tischner (2001) are the following:

- **Material efficient design:** optimization of the material input through substitution of raw material, light weight design, cut compatible design, miniaturization versus disassembling friendliness, multifunctionality and limitation to essential functions
- **Material compatible design:** priority to renewable material, abdication of products from endangered animals and plants, application of local material and secondary raw material
- **Energy efficient design:** reduction of the energy consumption in all stages of the product life cycle, substitution of exhaustible through renewable energy sources
- **Low-emission design:** selection of low emission material, e.g. avoidance of heavy metals
- **Durable design:** avoidance of disposable products, use of high-quality, repairable material and construction, modular design, principles of solid construction, timeless design, high handling and using comfort, possibility of retrofitting

- **Recycling compatible design:** disassembling friendly design, labelling of raw material, components and equipment, selection of recycling compatible material, avoidance of composites
- **Disposal compatible design:** avoidance of material whose disposal is associated with environmentally harmful emissions, application of biodegradable material, labelling and separability of harmful substances
- **Logistics compatible design:** reduction of volume and the weight of products and packaging

The basic idea behind it is to increase sales by bringing to the market products having both a good environmental performance (“social benefit”) as well as a good performance for the individual customer (“customer benefit”). This development will continue, from simple improvements to rethinking the system (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Four levels of environmental action (Schnitzer, 2002)

Although Eco-design is able to innovate the systems or the products of a company radically, it can also propose simpler solutions, with short term results.

Depending on the target establish by the company, four levels of application of the Eco-design can be distinguished, and therefore four types of different results:

- Level 1: Repair – small improvements only
- Level 2: Refine – improve the environmental performance of a product
- Level 3: Redesign – a new product is redesigned on the basis of an existing product
- Level 4: Rethink – develop new products to fulfil function based on new concepts

5.5 The 6 RE Philosophy

As an incentive for the optimization and redesign of products serves the “6 RE Philosophy”:

- **RE-THINK** the product and its functions, e.g. how the product may be used more efficiently.
- **RE-DUCE** energy and material consumption throughout the product’s life cycle.
- **RE-PLACE** harmful substances with more environmentally friendly alternatives.
- **RE-CYCLE**. Select materials that can be recycled, and build the product in a way that it can be easily disassembled for recycling.
- **RE-USE**. Design the product so parts can be used.
- **RE-PAIR**. Make the product easy to repair so that the product does not yet need to be replaced.

5.6 Strategies, Tools and Methodologies for Eco-design

The integration of environmental considerations into the product development process is vital for the success of Eco-design and even for product development in general. As product development processes and organisations differ from company to company, depending on their specific needs and requirements, the integration of Eco-design also differs.

A good starting point are the following key questions to identify the product’s most environmentally significant aspects on which the Eco-design strategy should be focused:

- What is the main purpose or application of your product?
- What are the most likely usage patterns?
- What is the intended lifetime, the usual lifetime?
- Who is the user? Business-to-business or business-to-consumer?
- What is the product size?

5.6.1 Tools for Eco-design

Most of the Eco-design tools were developed for the analysis of environmental aspects of existing products. One of the most established is the product eco balance or better known as Life cycle assessment (LCA). In practice LCA is rarely used because it is complex, time-consuming and thus expensive. In product development and designing more simple and not as time-consuming tools are being used, e.g. checklists.

The following graphic shows an overview of the most popular available Eco-design tools sorted regarding their complexity and their function. Basically four different tasks of for Eco-design helpful tools can be distinguished:

- Ecological analysis of strengths and weaknesses
- Priority-setting, selection of the most important potential for improvement
- Implementation: Support of design, brainstorming, detailing of ideas
- Balancing with other important criteria: cost-benefit-valuation, evaluation of cost-effectiveness

Figure 5 Categorization of Eco-design tools (Tischner, 2001)

As mentioned, checklists are a basic tool for Eco-design. They give advice on where to focus and what to do; they help to start thinking about certain environmental aspects. Repeated checks can also be a guideline for improvements.

Questions, e.g. regarding the material content of the product, help to understand how much you really know about your product. Knowing more about the product is the basis for quality and research to identify and implement product improvements.

Checklists are especially helpful for the analysis of strengths and weaknesses and for the detailing of the design. The following checklist is a good example (Tool C.9).

The bad news is that there exists no “cookbook” for Eco-design, as it is also about creativity and innovation. But, ISO/TR 14062:2002 gives guidelines for the integration of Eco-design in a product development process. Information on the ISO/TR 14062:2002 can be found here: http://www.iso.org/iso/catalogue_detail?csnumber=33020

Tool C.12 Eco-design checklist (Tischner, 2001)

Production phase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material/energy usage • Waste intensity • Reject rate • Productivity, effect • Material diversity • Transport intensity • Package intensity • Demand of space • Usage of pollutants
Using phase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material/energy usage • Size and weight • Demand of space • Cleaning complexity • Functions of self-control and optimization • Multifunctionality • Possibility for multiple printed panel • Possibility for conjoint benefits • Waste intensity • Pollutants • Durability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Trendy design ○ Valuation ○ Surface finish ○ Corrosion resistance ○ Possibility for maintenance ○ Reparability ○ Decomposability ○ Reliability ○ Robustness ○ Material fatigue and abrasion sensitivity ○ Modular construction and grade of standardisation ○ Flexibility to the technical progress ○ Possibilities for combination, variability
Return phase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material/energy usage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Material composition, complexity of the building structure ○ Decomposability, separability ○ Cleaning complexity ○ Material labelling ○ Possibility of “decreation” ○ Further usability, reusability ○ Possibility to collect and separate
Disposal phase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to compost and ferment • Burning characteristics • Environmental impacts of landfilling

5.6.2 Eco-design Strategies

Environmental design strategies are environmental improvement strategies tailored to a specific product's context and particular environmental impacts. Both strategies attempt to minimise environmental impacts and enhance design characteristics.

Among these strategies one can find a selection of low-impact materials, reduction of materials usage, optimization of production techniques, optimization of distribution systems, reduction of impacts during use, optimization of initial lifetime, and optimization of end-of-life systems (Schischke et al. 2005).

The selection and combination of strategies is an interdisciplinary team activity and a method on its own right.

Selection of low-impact materials

Decreasing hazardousness in the resources used can minimize the environmental impact at the product disposal stage. Selection of low-impact materials can be done either for the product or for the packaging, or for both.

Reduction in materials usage

Reduction on materials usage is based on a product's dimensions, weight and number of parts. It can also lead to the development of new techniques to avoid the use of some components like ventilation or cooling systems.

Optimization of production techniques

The production process should be investigated in order to improve environmental performance. Improvements can be obtained with material substitution, good housekeeping, on-site recycling and modification of technologies. An audit of the manufacturing plant can indicate where changes should be made in the production process.

Optimization of logistics system

Logistics during the whole life cycle of a product (raw materials transport, product distribution, and reverse logistics) has a significant impact on the environment. Companies should minimise the environmental impacts and associated economic costs of their logistics.

Reduction of impact during use

Substantial environmental gains can be made for many products by reducing the environmental impact during the use phase. Two key areas that should be addressed are water and energy consumption.

Appliances and other electrical equipment increasingly draw power when they are switched off or are not performing their primary function. This "standby power" provides remote control capability, network sensing, digital display or other features. Often, standby power is consumed simply because power supplies remain "on" while their appliances are switched "off".

Standby power can be reduced by an average of 75 % with cost-effective design changes and technological improvements. Savings up to 90 % can be achieved in many appliances without any reduction in services.

A reduction in energy consumption can also be achieved by reducing the power consumption of a product, replacing conventional batteries with solar energy systems or even using human power.

Optimization of the initial life stage – design for upgrade and reuse

The objective here is to increase the initial lifetime of a product so that it can be used for a longer period before being replaced. The main issue in this field is to focus not only on products themselves, but on the product within the system and the constraints in this system. Optimization for upgrade and reuse can be reached by:

- Designing for easy maintenance by, for example, incorporating simple and quickly detachable parts;
- Designing for upgradability, which is easier if the product is modular.

The extension of the original lifetime can lead to the establishment of a repair and maintenance service to supply spare parts and labour.

A product can become obsolete for the user for many reasons:

- Technical: the product is worn out and no longer functions properly
- Economic: new products have a lower level of “costs of ownership” (maintenance, energy, etc.)
- Ecological: new products have less harmful impact on the use phase (maintenance, energy, etc.)
- Aesthetical: new products have a nicer look, a more fashionable design, a better image
- Functional: new products fulfil functions better
- Psychological: old products have a negative emotional factor (unpleasant history); new products have a positive emotional factor.

Taking these into account, a product that overcomes these barriers can be designed. In particular, if one of the above reasons only concerns a part of a product, it can be designed to be easily upgraded, using modular design principles.

Optimization of end-of-life-system

This strategy is about reuse, remanufacturing, refurbishing, and recycling options. Optimization of end-of-life system implies that the collected products are undamaged before reuse and are a high standard.

Product components must be available or remanufactured for a long time.

New concept development

This Eco-design strategy differs from other strategies because it requires innovative thinking. A “Factor 4” or greater reduction in environmental impact is hard to achieve by modifications to existing products. The idea behind new concept development is to integrate and optimise product functions or to replace the product with a service. This potentially leads to the development of new products with new functions or new business patterns to meet the same market needs.

“New concept development” promotes thinking towards a sustainable future beyond the existing product.

5.6.3 Combination of strategies

The use of several different impact reduction strategies can produce better results than the application of a single one. In the process of product development, these strategies may include optimization of the service provided by the product, conservation of resources, and reduction of pollution, waste and damages.

The ecological aspects should also be included with other design criteria, and the choice of a specific design solution shall achieve a reasonable balance between environmental factors and other relevant considerations, such as safety and health, technical requirements for functionality, quality, and performance, and economic aspects, including manufacturing costs and marketability.

5.6.4 Conclusions

Eco-design is a multidisciplinary task and requires an adequate learning environment and creativity techniques.

Benefits deriving from the implementation of Eco-design can be summarized as follows:

- **Future orientation of the company**
Responsibility, motivation, corporate image, confidence of stakeholders, achieving better ratings;
- **Innovative products**
Multidisciplinary work, improving product quality, customer needs, optimizing functionality, new consumer segments;
- **Improved environmental performance**
Reduction of material and energy input, avoidance of waste and emissions, toxic products avoidance, compliance with environmental standards;
- **Improved cost structure**
Operational costs during use, purchase costs of energy, auxiliary and process materials, procurement costs, reducing costs for waste disposal;

6. Training course & manuals

RERAM has developed an applied training programme on resource efficiency. It is a complete training course, which comprises **lectures and practical exercises, designed to educate personnel with basic technical knowledge** on Cleaner Production principles, methods and improvement options.

The training material is based on the Austrian ÖKOPROFIT approach and was developed by Mr. Christian Angerbauer of ACECon e.U. Environmental & Efficiency Consulting on behalf of HCS Holzcluster Steiermark GmbH.

The training course was carried out as part of the **RERAM 'Training-of-Trainers Weeks'** in Lviv, Ukraine, 13-17 October 2014, and in Graz, Austria, 9-13 February 2015. With this 10 days training course, 17 experts from 11 organizations of 6 different countries successfully completed the training and received a certificate (see reports D2.1 'Transnational Trainings of Experts' and D4.1 'Capacity Building Activities').

The training course was furthermore applied during the **RERAM joint company trainings** (5 workshops, 1-3 days per workshop), which have been conducted in Ukraine, Georgia and Moldova as part of the enterprise checks to provide the participating woodworking companies with hands-on knowhow and guidance for the implementation of efficiency measures (see report D3.3 'Reality checks and benchmarking').

6.1 Training lectures

The training lectures include a series of presentations and exercises on Cleaner Production. They aim to raise awareness for the topic and provide knowledge about practical resource efficiency management in companies. The lectures are suitable to **train small teams of technical staff** for example in a company-internal training measure.

The exercises provide visual examples, where trainees have to apply the lectured knowledge and find themselves creative solutions. The exercises are of general nature and can easily be applied to any company.

The complete training lectures are available in English and Russian language (which was chosen for practical reasons to attain a broader audience in the ENP-EaP countries). The main CP introduction and several selected chapters have also been translated into Romanian and Georgian language. All lecture material is available online from: www.reram.eu

Tool L.1 Training lecture 'Introduction to Cleaner Production'

Sustainable management mindset values action
CP vs End of the Pipe
CP Options in general
Exercise 1: Mini case study

Tool L.2 Training lecture ‘Material Flow Analysis, Auditing’

How to perform a MFA & Exercise 2: MFA

Initial auditing / Reality check – How to perform the first company visit

Tool L.3 Training lecture ‘Waste management, Water management’

Waste Management

Water Management

Tool L.4 Training lecture ‘Eco-purchasing, GHS, MSDS’

Ecological Purchasing / Green procurement

Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS)

Exercise on Safety Data Sheets (MSDS)

Tool L.5 Training lecture ‘Energy analysis’

Energy analysis, conservation and management & Exercise

Guidelines on energy efficiency in selected areas

Tool L.6 Training lecture ‘Controlling’

Environmental Controlling & Exercise

6.2 Training manuals

The same knowhow provided in the lectures is also available in a more condensed form as manuals. These provide more extensive details and explanations and are therefore suitable for self-study by staff members. They also contain several exercises. These manuals are only available in English language and can be downloaded at www.reram.eu

Tool M.1 Manual 1 ‘Cleaner production’

Tool M.2 Manual 2 ‘Material Flow Analysis’

Tool M.3 Manual 3 ‘Waste management’

Tool M.4 Manual 4 ‘Corporate Energy Analysis’

Tool M.5 Manual 5 ‘Eco-Friendly Purchasing, Hazardous Materials’

Tool M.6 Manual 6 ‘Environmental Costs, Environmental Controlling’

7. Further Tools and Literature

7.1 Toolkits for Resource Efficiency

European Commission DG Growth, 2016. European Resource Efficiency Self-Assessment Tool (RESAT). <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/resat/>

JRC Joint Research Centre, 2016. Best Available Techniques reference documents (BREFs). <http://eippcb.jrc.ec.europa.eu/reference/>

UNEP RECP 2010. Pre SME Toolkit Industrial Handbook. www.unep.org/pdf/PRE-SME_handbook_2010.pdf

UNIDO 2008. Cleaner Production Toolkit www.unido.org/resources/publications/safeguarding-the-environment/industrial-energy-efficiency/cp-toolkit-english.html

7.2 Tools for Waste Reduction, Waste Management

EEPA & TVA, 2004. Waste Reduction Guide for Wood Furniture Industries. Workbook. US Environmental Protection Agency, Center for Environmental Research Information & Tennessee Valley Authority, Waste Management. Cincinnati, Ohio & Knoxville, Tennessee, US. <http://infohouse.p2ric.org/ref/01/00418.pdf>

Envirowise, 2001. Furniture essentials: environmental information for furniture manufacturers. Good Practice Guide GG 289. Harwell International Business Centre, UK. www.wrap.org.uk/sites/files/wrap/GG289.pdf

Envirowise, 2001. Savings from waste minimization in furniture manufacturing. Good Practice Guide GG 290. Harwell International Business Centre, UK. www.wrap.org.uk/sites/files/wrap/GG290.pdf

WRAP Waste and Resources Action Programme, 2003. Wood waste recycling in furniture manufacturing: a good practice guide. Banbury, UK. www.wrap.org.uk

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